

ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE ADHESIVES FOR CFRP COMPOSITES BASED ON NICKEL NANOSTRANDS AND CARBON NANOTUBES

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Keywords: *structural adhesives, electrically conductive, nickel nanostrands, carbon nanotubes*

1 Introduction

Nowadays satellite antennas (Fig. 1) are made of CFRP composites as they are light weight and display outstanding dimensional stability compared to metal structures. Conductive structural adhesives are needed to ensure electrical continuity of adhesively bonded parts and to eliminate supplemental time-consuming operations like inter-panel jumper cabling or silver brazing.

Recently we reported highly conductive epoxy composites based on carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [1, 2]. According to Hansen [3] nickel nanostrands (NiNSs) are a very promising filler to produce highly conductive structural adhesives. In the present study we investigate the influence of the nanofiller type and concentration on the adhesive mechanical and electrical performances.

Figure1 Satellite antenna (courtesy of MDA)

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Epoxy resin Epon 862 was purchased from Miller Stepheneson and nickel nanostrands from Conductive Composites. Single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) were provided by Nikkiso Co. All materials were used as received. Hysol EA 9392 adhesive system from Henkel was used as reference.

2.2 Nanofiller dispersion

SWCNTs were dispersed by an optimized three-roll milling (EXAKT 80E, EXAKT Technologies, Inc.) in Epon 862 [1]. NiNSs and the resin were hand mixed then screened through a wire-mesh with 55x80 mesh size.

2.3 Sample preparation

Single lap-joints with dimensions shown in Figure 2 were prepared using aluminum 2024 T3 and EX1515/YSH-50A (cyanate ester resin/pitch based CF) CFRP adherents. The aluminum coupons were cleaned with acetone in an ultrasonic bath then etched in chromic acid for 30 min at 65 °C. CFRP coupons were grit-blasted for 4 sec at 40 psi using 220 mesh alumina. Bond-line of 0.2 mm was ensured by glass beads.

Figure 2 Single lap-joint; dimensions in mm.

2.4 Testing methods

The resistance of the lap-joint was measured using a four wire method. For the electrical measurements a Keithley 6220 DC current source and a Keithley 2182A nanovoltmeter were used. The apparent shear strength was determined according to ASTM D1002-01 on a MTS 100 kN testing machine. The dispersion of the fillers in the fractured samples was observed on a Hitachi S4700 SEM.

3 Results and discussion

3.1. Electrical conductivity

Figure 3 presents the SEM images of NiNSs - highly conductive metallic filler but with high density, and SWCNTs - highly conductive carbon material with low density and high aspect ratio.

Figure 3 SEM micrographs of NiNSs (a) and SWCNTs (b)

Figure 4 Conductivity vs. CNT loading

3.1.1 Carbon nanotube based adhesives

Using carefully selected CNTs and optimized dispersion methods we reported record electrical conductivities in Epon 862 at CNT loadings less than 1 wt% (Figure 4) [1, 2]. Observing Figure 4 it is clear that for a conductivity of say 1 S/m one need only 0.045 wt% of SWCNTs or 0.35% of MWCNTs. Low CNT loadings ensure minimal interference with the adhesive mechanical performance while displaying high electrical conductivity.

3.1.2 Nickel nanostrand based adhesives

While the electrical conductivity of CNT based composites display a classical percolation behavior those based on NiNSs are not. For example, single-lap joints made with aluminum adherents (with an overlap area of 4.75 cm² Figure 2) and a conductive adhesive containing 5 vol% (27 wt%) of NiNSs has a typical resistance around 1 mΩ. Based on the measured resistances and the bond geometry we expected the following resistivity:

$$\rho = R \frac{A}{t} = 0.001 \Omega \frac{4.75 \text{ cm}^2}{0.02 \text{ cm}} \sim 0.24 \Omega \text{cm}$$

where: ρ - resistivity, A- overlap area and t - bond line thickness.

Unexpectedly, the volume resistivity of a plate (50x50x1.6 mm) made of conductive adhesive was impossible to measure using our van der Pauw setup [1]. Based on the above calculated resistivity,

forcing currents up to 100 mA through the sample should not be a problem, but it was impossible to force a very low current of 10 nA at the maximum source voltage (105 V). This means that NiNS at 27%wt (~5 vol%) loading did not reach the percolation threshold in the bulk. Therefore, the very low resistance of the lap joints can be explained by the "short circuits" caused by the large agglomerates bridging from one side of the lap joint to other side. To assess the particle size distribution in the conductive adhesive, the resin was removed using acetone washing. Figure 5a presents typical NiNSs agglomerates with an average diameter slightly over 1 mm.

Figure 5 NiNS agglomerates. (a) direct mix of the as received NiNSs; (b) after screening over a wire cloth of 55x 80 mesh size; (1 division = 1 mm)

Following the manufacturer recommendations the mixture of adhesive and NiNSs was screened over a wire cloth of 55x80 mesh size to eliminate large agglomerates. Indeed, by screening the agglomerate size is decreased from more than 1 mm in diameter

(Figure 5a) to around 0.2 mm in diameter (Figure 5b). These agglomerates are not compact metal particles as they may appear from Figure 5 but some kind of elastic and porous structures shown in the SEM image on Figure 6.

Figure 6 SEM image of NiNS agglomerates

Once the large agglomerates are removed the bond resistance jumped almost 3 orders of magnitude from 1 m Ω to 0.53 Ω (Figure 7). Analyzing Figure 7 it is unexpected that the bond resistance is almost the same over a wide range of NiNS loadings. These results further sustain the fact that low resistances of the lap joints are caused by short circuits and not percolation.

Figure 7 Lap-joint resistances vs. NiNS loading

To prove this agglomeration-controlled electrical conductivity we have produced single-lap joints with

gradually increasing bond-line thicknesses and we measured their resistance. Considering the usual equation of the electrical resistance - $R = \frac{\rho t}{A}$ - we expected a linear dependence on the bond-line thickness (t). The resistances of lap joints with bond-line thickness of 0.25, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8 mm were 28 mΩ, 1.7Ω, 560Ω and $> 10^{10}$ Ω respectively. The dependence of the above resistances on the bond-line thickness is quite far from being linear.

3.2. Apparent shear strength

Figures 8 and 9 present SEM images of fractured lap joints made with adhesives based on NiNSs and SWCNTs, respectively.

Figure 8 Fracture surface of the NiNS containing adhesive

Figure 9 Fracture surface of the SWCNT containing adhesive

Table 1 presents the shear strength (SS) and the bond-resistance (R) of single-lap joints prepared with aluminum and CFRP adherents and different adhesives. Using NiNSs and SWCNTs the resistance of the lap joints made with aluminum adherents are 10 and 8 orders of magnitude lower than those prepared with the reference Hysol EA 9392 adhesive. For lap joints made of CFRP adherents, the resistance compared to that of the reference adhesive decreased by 8 and 10 orders of magnitude.

Table 1 Mechanical and electrical properties of lap joints

No	Adhesive	SS(SD), MPa	R(SD), Ω
<i>Aluminium adherents</i>			
1	Reference: Hysol 9392	28.4 (0.3)	$>10^{10}$
2	Epon862, 27%NiNSs	28.3 (0.5)	0.53 (0.3)
3	Epon862, 0.5% SWCNTs	30.1 (1.3)	83 (14)
<i>CFRP adherents</i>			
4	Reference: Hysol 9392	18.1 (3.9)	$>10^{10}$
5	Epon862, 27%NiNSs	14.6 (0.8)	46.3(15.7)
6	Epon862, 0.5% SWCNTs	12.9(1.4)	1.5(0.7)

While the shear strength of the new conductive adhesive exceeds that of the reference adhesive for aluminum adherents, for CFRP adherents it is unexpectedly low. The fractured lap joints revealed different failure mechanisms for the two types of adherents. In the case of the aluminum the lap joint showed cohesive failure as can be observed in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Picture of a fractured lap joint made with aluminum adherents

In the case of CFRP adherents the failure occurs in the adherent that explains the lower shear strength compared to aluminum (Figure 11).

Figure 11 SEM image of a fractured lap joint made with CFRP adherents.

Furthermore, we have evidence of chemical reactions between the adhesive and the cyanate ester matrix. These reactions could affect the shear strength of the bond and explain the variations of the shear strength for the CFRP adherents.

3.3. Influence of the surface preparation

From Figure 11 it is clear that all the defects in the plies adjacent to the adhesive layer will strongly influence the mechanical performance of the bonded joint. Proper surface preparation is mandatory to obtain high bond strength. However, surface preparation will alter the first ply and defects created in this process will influence the shear strength. Furthermore, in order to increase the electrical conductivity the resin layer covering the carbon fibers should be completely removed but without damaging them. We investigated hand-sanding using

320 grit-size alumina paper and grit blasting with alumina of 220 grit size.

Figure 12 a-1 and a-2 presents the SEM images of the hand sanded samples. Observing the deep scratches on Figure 12 a-2, it is clear that even light sanding is quite damaging for the carbon fibers. Furthermore, the variability of the applied pressure during hand sanding will produce less uniform surface roughness. Grit blasting on the other hand produces uniform surface roughness as it can be observed from the low magnification images in Figures b-1, c-1 and d-1. SEM images of samples grit blasted for 2, 4 and 6 seconds are shown in Figures 12 b, c and d respectively. Observing the images in Figure 12 b-2, c-2 and d-2 reveals that by increasing the duration of grit blasting more and more carbon fibers are exposed (green islands). Table 2 presents the shear strength of single-lap joints with different surface preparation. The shear strength of the lap joints prepared with grit blasting for 4 sec and those prepared by sanding are very close, even if grit blasting results in more uniform roughness than sanding. However excessive blasting for 6 sec results in decreased shear strength.

Table 2 Influence of surface preparation on the shear strength of the lap joints made with the reference adhesive

Description	Shear strength MPa (SD)
Grit blasting, 4 sec	18.9(3.1)
Grit blasting, 6 sec	17.0 (2.7)
Hand sanding, 320 grit	18.5(2.6)

Figure 12 SEM images of CFRP adherents with different surface preparation (details in the text)

3.4. Resistance variation during thermal cycling

In orbit, satellite antennas undergo thermal cycling with temperatures that range from -150 °C to +150°C. Single-lap joints exposed to thermal cycling made with conductive adhesive based on NiNSs displayed large variations of resistance, while those based on SWCNTs showed only a slight variation (Figure 13).

Analyzing one thermal cycle (Figure 14) it is clear that large resistance variations occur only above the T_g (70°C) of the adhesive. It seems that high mobility of the cured resin chains and the increased CTE at temperatures over the T_g contribute to the increase of the distance between two NiNSs at the contact points, hence increasing the resistance of the conductive network. Below T_g the whole system is less "mobile" therefore less variations in the resistance.

Furthermore, if the sample is kept at 150°C for more than 2 hours the resistance is decreasing to a much lower values (the third cycle on Figure 15). This means that over the T_g the NiNSs network tends to rearrange itself towards a lower resistance configuration. This configuration is quite stable as the resistance displays only small variations during subsequent thermal cycles (Figure 15 - 4th cycle).

Figure 14 Variation of the bond resistance during thermal cycling

Figure 15 Variation of the bond resistance during thermal cycling

Figure 13 Variation of the bond resistance during thermal cycling

4 Conclusions

We successfully formulated highly conductive adhesives based on NiNSs and SWCNTs. While SWCNTs display classical percolation behavior, NiNSs display an anomalous behavior. Our experimental results strongly suggest that the conductivity of the adhesives based on NiNSs are controlled by short-circuits caused large enough agglomerations that can span from adherent to the other. The resistances presented in Table 1 indicate that metal nanoparticles perform better with metal adherents while carbon nanomaterials are more suitable for CFRP adherents.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the support from MDA Corporation and the valuable discussions with Erick Charbonneau. This research was generously supported by Composites Atlantic, CRIAQ and NSERC CRD grant.

References

[1] I.D. Rosca, S.V. Hoa "Highly conductive multiwall carbon nanotube and epoxy composites produced by three-roll milling" *Carbon*, **47** (2009) 1958-68.

[2] I.D. Rosca, S.V. Hoa "Conductive nanocomposites based on mass produced carbon nanotubes and epoxy resin" Proceedings of the American Society for Composites, Technical Conference, 24th, Newark, Delaware, USA 2009.

[3] N. Hansen, O.A. Adams, K.L. DeVries, A. Goff and G. Hansen "Investigation of electrically conductive structural adhesives using nickel nanostrands" *J. Adhesion Sci Technol* **25(19)** (2011) 2659-70.

[4] N Hu, Z Masuda, G. Yamamoto, H Fukunaga, T. Hashida, J. Qiu "Effect of fabrication process on electrical properties of polymer/multi-wall carbon nanotube nanocomposites" *Composites: Part A* **39** (2008) 893-903.

[5] J.B. Bai, A. Allaoui "Effect of the length and the aggregate size of MWNTs on the improvement efficiency of the mechanical and electrical properties of nanocomposites-experimental investigation" *Composites Part A* **34(8)** (2003) 689-694.

[6] A Allaoui, S Bai, H.M Cheng, J.B Bai "Mechanical and electrical properties of a MWNT/epoxy composite" *Composites Science and Technology*, **62(15)**, (2002) 1993-1998.

[7] J.K.W. Sandler, J.E. Kirk, I.A. Kinloch, M.S.P. Shaffer, A.H. Windle "Ultra-low electrical percolation threshold in carbon-nanotube-epoxy composites" *Polymer* **44(19)** (2003) 5893-5899.

[8] Jing Li, Pui-Shan Wong, Jang-Kyo Kim "Hybrid nanocomposites containing carbon nanotubes and graphite nanoplatelets" *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **483-484** (2008) 660-663.

[9] J. Li, P. C. Ma, W. S. Chow, C. K. To, B. Z. Tang and J.-K. Kim "Correlations between Percolation Threshold,

Dispersion State, and Aspect Ratio of Carbon Nanotubes" *Adv Funct Mater* 2007 **17**, 3207.

[10] M. H. G. Wichmann, J. Sumfleth, B. Fiedler, F. H. Gojny, K. Schulte "Multiwall carbon nanotube/epoxy composites produced by a masterbatch process" *Mech Comp Mat* 2006 **42**, 395.

[11] Sheng Tian, Fangjin Cui, Xiaodong Wang "New type of piezo-damping epoxy-matrix composites with multi-walled carbon nanotubes and lead zirconate titanate" *Materials Letters* 2008 **62**, 3859.